

EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT AND MODEL DEVELOPMENT OF FRP SANDWICH PANELS SUBJECTED TO OUT-OF-PLANE IMPACT LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Fibre reinforced composites are lightweight, strong materials that are increasingly used in all sorts of applications. When loaded in-plane, the material is very strong due to the profitable properties of the fibres. Therefore, the design is normally such that the predominant loading condition is in-plane. However, out-of-plane loading is not always avoidable, especially in incidental loadings such as collisions or impact. Then the relatively weak resin-dominated properties are addressed. There is much less research on the behavior of composites in these conditions. In a joint industry project in a Dutch open innovation alliance “Groot Composiet”, this issue was addressed.

The behaviour of two types of composite sandwich panels, thin and thick under impact was studied both experimentally and numerically. The thin sandwich panels are mostly representative for applications in ships, while the thick panels could be applied as a bridge. Drop tower experiments were performed on several designs specific to the partners in the project. Delamination in the skin and failure within the core material was identified.

Prior to the project numerical models existed that could predict these types of damages very accurately. However, these models are very computationally demanding. Therefore, two numerical models were developed within this project for delamination and core failure prediction. The main focus of these models was to provide relatively quick, but reasonably accurate, finite element techniques.

Sandwich composite panels can show a high resistance to impact. The panels developed by the partners in the project without exception behaved very well, normally only showing a localized damage.

Delaminations were well predicted with the numerical model. Core failure could be predicted with sufficient accuracy for panels with a structural foam core. The results for non-structural foams were more sensitive to material and loading variations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced polymer composites (FRP) are increasingly used in heavily loaded applications such as bridges and ships. The material offers a strong and lightweight alternative to the conventional materials such as steel and concrete. Furthermore, fibre reinforced composites show a favourable behaviour with respect to maintenance. The strength of FRP lies mainly in in-plane loading conditions, where the fibres provide a strong loading path. However, out-of-plane loading cannot always be avoided. For example in incidental loading, such as collisions, impact or slamming, out-of-plane loading will occur. These loading conditions are often considered a hazard for the composite structure. Within a project in the open innovation alliance “Groot Composiet” a combination of tests and numerical model development was done to decrease this associated feeling of risk and to show that good design or clever use of materials can improve the behaviour.

2 PROJECT DEFINITION

Both the shipbuilding industry and the civil engineering industry (mainly bridge building) were involved in the project. Of course each of these applications have different demands for loadings, geometry etc. But each of them can suffer from (incidental) out-of-plane loading, such as slamming, collisions, impact of dropped objects etc. This loading addresses the weak matrix dominated properties of FRP. The aim of the project was to assess fibre reinforced sandwich materials in these out-of-plane loading conditions and develop numerical models that can predict damage due to this loading at limited computational costs. For a generic approach two basic configurations were chosen, thick and thin sandwich panels. The thick sandwich panels are representative for infrastructural applications such as bridges, while the thin sandwich panels are more representative for shipbuilding applications. Furthermore, partners could have their own more impact resistant concepts tested.

2.1 Material selection

Even though the applications studied within the project were quite different, the materials used within these applications were somewhat similar. To decrease the effort of material parameter determination and to enable as much as possible a connection between the different applications it was decided by the project partners to reside to the same materials. The basis of the skins was a non-crimp [0,90] E-glass with a Synolite 1967-X-1 resin. The core material was either a PU35 or an Airex C70.55 (PVC).

2.2 Thick specimen

The base configuration of the thick specimens consisted of 12 layers of 1200 gr E-glass Synolite skins of about 10 mm thick. The core of the base configuration was made from the non-structural PU35 foam. The total thickness of the panel was about 200 mm.

Next to the base configurations two partners provided their own more impact resistant panels. Main difference between the base configuration and these panels were the use of webs between the two skins of the sandwich. The complete thick specimen group consisted of:

- 3 base configuration panels
- 3 panels according to the concept of partner 1
- 2 panels according to the concept of partner 2

2.3 Thin specimen

The thin base configuration consisted of two 3 mm thick skins of 6 layers of 600 gr E-glass and a PVC core. The total panel was about 67 mm thick. In this group one additional concept was brought in by a project partner with the same general set-up, but using a more impact resistant resin. The complete thin specimen group consisted of:

- 3 base configuration panels
- 1 panel according to the concept of partner 3

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The development of failure models cannot be done without some validation. As such, this project combined the model development with impact experiments. Next to validation, these experiments also provided a good way to compare the different concepts that were introduced by the project partners. Of course, each result is only as good as the model input. Therefore, some material tests were performed to assess the material parameters and the distribution in the parameters.

3.1 Material tests

Material tests have been performed on both the two core foam materials (PU and PVC) and on the laminate. For the laminate, due to the modelling strategy, it was decided to focus on laminate parameters and interlaminar parameters and not on laminae parameters. This means both the 3 and the 10 mm biaxial laminates were tested in tension in the 0 direction and in [45,-45] direction.

Furthermore, the fracture energy of the midplane of each laminate was determined. The foam material was tested in tension, shear, compression and for fracture energy.

All material tests were performed according to standards, whether ASTM or ISO. Table 1 gives an overview of the standards used for testing.

Material	Parameter	Standard
<i>PU and PVC</i>	Tensile strength and modulus	ASTM 3574
	Shear strength and modulus	ISO 1922
	Compressive strength and modulus	ASTM 3574
	Fracture energy	ASTM D5045
Glass fibre laminates 3 mm and 10 mm	Tensile strength and modulus [0,90]	ISO 527
	Tensile strength and modulus [45,-45]	ISO527
	Fracture energy	ISO 15024

Table 1: Standards used in tests for material parameter determination

Figure 1 shows some of the tests. When comparing both foams it was seen that there was normally about 10% spreading between the mean and the extreme values. The structural PVC foam showed slightly more spreading than the PU foam that is normally used for shaping. The largest difference in behaviour of the two foams was seen in the compressive tests, in which the PU foam showed a clear constraining effect at the loading plates (leading to a convex shaped specimen), while the PVC showed a more uniform compressive behaviour (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Examples of the material tests (top foam fracture energy test; bottom left and mid laminate tensile test [0/90] and bottom right the 10 mm thick laminate fracture energy test)

Figure 2: Difference in compressive behavior of PU (left) and PVC (right)

The 3 mm and 10 mm glass fibre reinforced laminate results also showed results with quite some variation, especially in the determination of the fracture energy. Overall differences between the 3 mm and 10 mm laminates were not extremely large for the [0/90] tensile test and for the fracture energy test. However, the laminate thickness had a large effect on the tensile properties of the [45/-45] specimens, with differences up to 45% between the two specimens. The main material parameters are shown in Table 2. For the numerical analyses of Paragraph 4, the properties found for the foam were used. The laminate material tests were not available at the time of the analyses so these parameters were estimated from earlier projects. A comparison of the values later on showed that these estimations were reasonably close to the values found in the material tests, so no rerun of the analyses was done.

property	PU	PVC	FRP 3 mm (first value in [0,90]; second value [45,-45])	FRP 10 mm (first value in [0,90]; second value [45,-45])
E tensile [MPa]	12.9	52.9	8290; 3428	7075; 4947
σ tensile [MPa]	0.22	0.90	477;110	424;77
E compressive [MPa]	4.7	35.1	-	-
σ compressive [MPa]	0.23	0.85	-	-
Mode I fracture energy [J/m ²]	54.1	208.2	579	626

Table 2: Material properties

3.2 Impact test set-up

Since the aim of the project was to study the behaviour of composite materials in sandwich structures subjected to dynamic out-of-plane loading, drop tower impact experiments were used for validation of the developed material modelling and the comparison between the different concepts provided by the project partners. Due to the two main specimen categories two different drop tower set-ups were used. However, the concept of both tests is the same. A guided half spherical impactor (diameter 400 mm) with a certain weight is dropped onto a two sided simply supported test specimen of 1.5x1m. The span of the simply supported specimen is 1 m. The specimen is strapped to prevent it from becoming loose from the supports. The drop weight is different for the two categories of panels. The combination of drop weight and height determines the amount of energy subjected to a test specimen. Figure 3 shows the drop tower used for the thick specimens.

For each concept of test specimen (see Paragraph 2.2 and 2.3) one panel was tested in a base configuration so a comparison could be made between the different concepts. The other panels of that specific concept were tested in different configurations, either with a higher impact energy or at a specific location of the panel (e.g. on a web or directly next to a web).

Figure 3: Drop tower set-up for thick specimen. (A) is the impactor and (B) the test specimen

Each test was filmed using a high speed camera. Two accelerometers were attached to the drop weight to determine impact velocities. After a test the tested specimen was visually inspected. Furthermore a metal ring was used to acoustically look for damages. Some specimens were cut after this inspection for further assessment.

3.3 Thick specimen drop tests

The base testing configuration of the thick panels consisted of a drop weight of 1060 kg that was dropped from a height of 0.5 m. The base panel of this configuration showed some clear damages. A delamination in the top laminate was found at the impactor location. The PU foam core was badly damaged, which is to be expected from a non-structural foam (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Damages in plain thick sandwich panel (left delamination in top laminate, right large area of debonding between top laminate and foam core)

Both other concepts in the thick specimen configuration had some connection between the upper and lower laminate by means of webs. This provides a clear improvement of the specimen behavior. Delaminations in the upper laminate were still found and were even somewhat larger than the one found in the plain sandwich. In some of the panels it could be seen that this delamination was more asymmetrical due to the presence of webs in one direction. However, no core damage was found except for some very localized damages on webs. It can thus be stated that the web stiffened panels behave much better in impact, showing only local damage without structural failure.

3.4 Thin specimen drop test

For the thin specimen the base configuration was a dropweight of 258 kg from a height of 0.45 m. In these conditions some possible foam failure (around 1 m²) was estimated based on the high speed

video images and tapping of the panel with a metal ring. Unfortunately none of the thin specimens was cut after testing. The other concept in the thin specimen group had a more impact resistant matrix material. Tapping of the panel and studying the high speed camera images suggests that this panel showed less than half of the amount of failure of the other panel. However, since no panel was cut, no definite conclusion can be drawn.

For the thin specimen also one specimen was tested at a higher loading condition, with an impactor weight of 396 kg dropped from a height of 0.5 m. This panel showed clear core failure (Figure 5). From the high speed images this failure is seen to originate from the bottom laminate foam interface (Figure 6), expanding towards the support and the top of the specimen. After cutting the panel it was seen that below the impactor also a conical shape was punched out of the foam core (Figure 7).

Figure 5: Failure of thin specimen at high impact loading

Figure 6: Location of failure initiation thin specimen

Figure 7: Punched cone shape failure below impactor

4 NUMERICAL MODELLING

Several numerical models already exist to simulate the failure behaviour of laminated composites and sandwiches. Many of these models either focus on the failure modes observed in in-plane loading and/or require very fine meshes. When studying large structures in dynamic out-of-plane loading conditions these models are not practically applicable. Therefore, in this project relative quick, coarse models for the phenomena seen in impact situations were developed, that are still fairly accurate.

In the drop tower experiments several failure mechanisms were seen. Delamination occurred between layers of the skin laminates (indicated by 1 in Figure 8). The foam core of the sandwiches showed different types of failure. Either starting at an edge of the panel at the foam laminate interface and growing towards the centre of the panel (interface skin-core debonding, 3) or starting more in the centre of the panel (also at the foam laminate interface) and growing into the foam and along the interface towards the edge of the panel (shear failure, 2). Figure 8 shows these main failure mechanisms. Next to this some web crushing was seen in the web stiffened panels. However, since this was very much dependent on the actual concept of the panel and very localised, this failure mechanism is not taken into account in the modelling.

Figure 8: Failure mechanisms in specimen (1: delamination, 2 and 3: different types of foam failure)

4.1 Modelling techniques

The delamination modelling is based on the modelling developed within earlier projects (Dycoss). A more elaborate description of this model is given in [1] and [2]. After the Dycoss projects the model was implemented in the LS-DYNA Finite Element package as part of the contact tiebreak models (e.g. *CONTACT_AUTOMATIC_ONE_WAY_SURFACE_TO_SURFACE_TIEBREAK OPTION=7). Failure is initiated when the failure parameter, f , in Equation 1 is equal to 1. Failure propagation is based on a linear softening behaviour based on fracture energies (Equation 2). A schematic representation of the model is shown in Figure 9.

This model does require relatively small elements to ensure that delamination propagation is distributed over a sufficient number of elements. Larger elements can be used if the peak stresses in both normal and shear direction are defined to be dependent on the element size. In general it can be said that lower peak stresses, combined with equal fracture energies, should be used for coarser meshes.

$$\text{initiation} \quad f = \left(\frac{\max(F_n, 0)}{F_{n,\max}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{F_s}{F_{s,\max} (1 - \sin(\phi) \min(0, F_n))} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{propagation} \quad (0 < D < 1) \quad \left(\frac{\Delta u_n}{D \Delta u_{n,ult} + \Delta u_{n,ini}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta u_s}{D \Delta u_{s,ult} + \Delta u_{s,ini}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

Figure 9: Representation of mixed-mode failure initiation and propagation delamination model

Foam failure can be modelled e.g. by smeared crack based models. However, these all require very fine meshes especially when element deletion is included in explicit finite element programs. Within this project it was studied if the cracking of the foam could be completely decoupled from the normal continuum elements. To achieve this, cohesive zone elements were placed on all sides of the continuum elements (Figure 10). The cohesive zone elements provide the cracking possibility of the foam. This approach of course does limit the freedom of the foam for cracking. Cracking can only occur along the element lines. However, for relative coarse analyses, this is sufficient. Cracking is governed by the selection of a traction separation law for the cohesive zone elements. In this project one scalable curve for both normal and shear behaviour is used. This did not prove to be the best option. Furthermore, the cohesive zone elements, based on the initial contact stiffness and their size, provided an artificial flexibility in the foam material. It was seen that it was best too choose a high normalized contact stiffness and a not too refined mesh.

Figure 10: Solid element mesh in which the solid elements are connected by a cohesive zone element mesh

4.2 Results

To limit the computational effort only one quarter of a complete panel is modelled. Symmetry conditions have been taken into account at the symmetry planes. The support is modelled by constraining all displacements on the bottom skin laminate at the location of the support. The drop weight is modelled as a rigid body with an initial velocity. Gravity is taken into account. Material parameters as given in Table 2 are used. Figure 11 shows the model for the thick specimen, including a detailed view with some of the cohesive zone elements and the delamination modelling.

Figure 11: Finite element model of thick panel

For the thick specimen the base configuration with a drop height of 0.5 m was analysed. It was seen that the predicted failure was very dependent on the material properties used. With the original parameters failure in the numerical analysis initiated at the outside of the panel at the interface between the top skin and the foam approximately halfway between the impact location and the support (Figure 12), growing towards the centre of the panel and the bottom skin (Figure 12). This was not the failure behaviour seen in the test (see Paragraph 3.3). The analysis was repeated with 75% of the material parameter values. This analysis did show a damage mode which was much more in agreement with the experimental results (Figure 13). Other variations of parameters and laminate thicknesses also showed a clear dependence on the properties. In general it can be said that if the foam is relatively strong compared to the skin (so either higher values for the foam properties, or thinner skins) the failure behaviour was a shear band in the foam extending in foam/skin interface failure, whereas with relatively weaker foam properties the failure mode resembled the experimentally found failure mode.

In all analyses a delamination was predicted in the top skin layer of approximately 200-300 cm². In the experiment a delamination area of 225 cm² was seen.

Figure 12: Failure initiation (top) and propagation (bottom) of the thick specimen analysis with the original material parameters

Figure 13: Failure pattern with foam properties 75% of original values

In the analyses of the thin specimens (drop height 396 kg from 0.5 m) the results are far less dependent on material parameters and much more in line with the experimental results. With the original parameters the crack in the foam initiates at the interface between the bottom skin and the foam approximately 100 mm from the centre of the panel (Figure 14). In the experiment a shearband was seen originating approximately 120 mm from the panel centre, so the crack initiation location is well captured. Also crack propagation (Figure 14) is well captured although the crack in the numerical analysis does not propagate all the way towards the edge of the specimen. The cone that was punched from the foam in the experiment was not seen in the analysis. No delamination was found in either experiment or in the analysis.

The main changes that occurred in the failure in the parameter variation study were the location of the shear band in the panel. When the foam is relatively weaker, the shear band occurs more towards the supports, which is less in agreement with the experiments. Furthermore it was seen that if the foam is relatively strong (so higher values for the foam properties or thinner skins) some sort of punching failure was seen below the impactor (Figure 15).

Figure 14: Failure initiation (top) and growth (bottom) of thin specimen

Figure 15: Punching type of failure below impactor for analysis with 125% of the value of the foam parameters

9 CONCLUSIONS

Although the project was limited to only impact loading on some simply supported panels it can be concluded that design for impact is possible. All the partner concepts behaved better than the base configurations. The numerical tools that were developed seem capable of predicting the main damage mechanisms. However, the tools behave best for larger damages and stronger materials. Weaker materials are very sensitive to small variations in the material properties, which are not captured with the numerical tools.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P.P.M. Lemmen and G.J. Meijer, *Failure prediction tool theory and user manual*, TNO Report 200-CMC-R0018, 2001
- [2] J.H.A. Schipperen, *Validation of a progressive failure prediction tool for a dynamically loaded three dimensional composite ship structure*, *Proceedings of the 15th European conference on composite materials ECCM15, Venice, Italy, 24-28 June 2012*